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FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS IN SCHOOL BIOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ УЧЕНИКОВ В ШКОЛЬНОМ БИОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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Abstract

The article In general education schools discusses the organization of work on the formation of professional competencies of students, the formation of motivation in the direction of students to a profession, the technology for the formation of professional competencies of students in biology lessons and extracurricular activities.

Аннотация

В статье В общеобразовательных школах обсуждаются организация работы по формированию профессиональных компетенций учащихся, формирование мотивации при направлении учащихся к профессии, технологии формирования профессиональных компетенций учащихся на уроках биологии и внеурочной деятельности .

Keywords: school, professional competence, vocational guidance, content of students' vocational guidance, conditions, methods of activity, opportunities for vocational guidance in the subject "Biology".

Ключевые слова: школа, профессиональная компетентность, профориентация, содержание профориентации студентов, условия, методы деятельности, возможности профориентации по предмету «Биология».

In accordance with the requirements of the state educational standard of general education, the career guidance program for students should be presented as a separate structural element in the main curriculum of the school. Therefore, a difficult task is assigned to the teaching staff and the management of general education schools: to create conditions for the active participation of each student in certain types of activities during and outside the lesson, which will help them in their further educational and professional development. start your business effectively. The main idea of career guidance in a modern school is socio-pedagogical and psychological support, taking into account the personal characteristics, abilities, values and interests of students, on

the one hand, and the needs of society and the labor market. Requirements, on the other hand, is to create the necessary conditions for the formation of professional competencies based on socio-professional self-determination.

The main goal is to create conditions for ensuring the professional competence and competitiveness of students at the stage of general secondary education.

Responsibilities: Students have:

- create an objective image of yourself as a personal subject of your activity (primarily educational and professional);

- formation of ideas about the needs of modern society among graduates of general education schools and vocational education institutions;

Student acquisition:

- methods of creating and implementing personal educational programs;
- effective ways of applying the forms of career guidance activities in practice;
- work with open sources of information about the labor market, trends in its development and the prospective needs of the economy of the region where students live and the country as a whole, the formation of decision-making methods for choosing an individual professional direction.

Based on unchanging general goals, the specific goals and objectives of each school depend on the needs of a particular profession, the severity of these needs, as well as the capabilities and conditions of a particular region or city. The successful implementation of the tasks set largely depends on the quality of work in each area. It is necessary to start work directly with that essential part that connects the teaching staff with this work.

The content of students' professional orientation at the level of general secondary education ensures the development of students' activities and the formation of their ability to make a worthy and responsible choice of a future profession.

As part of the curriculum, for the development of student activity, the acquisition of educational materials, knowledge in various areas during classroom and extracurricular activities, as well as the participation of students in various methods of activity: circles of the future, design and research activities. out through attraction.

In this regard, the use of modern pedagogical technologies (technologies of social cooperation, technologies for the formation of individual educational trajectories, gaming technologies, etc.) increases the activity of students at the stage of choosing a profession and self-confidence in a dynamically changing world arises from the needs that create the possibility of realization.

Teachers point of view in terms of motivation, education and development processes can be controlled _ That's all because of students in grades 6-8 young function because of the most comfortable passing time do not send important _ This period in the future professional motivation for the foundation lay important _ Grade hours and possible as long as in classes students other in occupations work contents with presenting , their inner being open to give it is necessary.

Career guidance in the study of botany and zoology (grades 6-7) focuses on a preliminary analysis of classes and a clear definition of two main issues: the content of the lesson and the necessary skills and abilities. In grades 8-9, attention should be paid to self-assessment, introspection, and the development of professional interests. In grades 10-11, the process of professional self-determination is completed, and at this time it is necessary to diagnose the compliance of professional requirements with the abilities of the students themselves.

When organizing the educational process at school, a natural science teacher should pay special attention to the formation of professional competencies. In addition, this activity has its own characteristics in each discipline. To form the desire to work with natural objects, consider the technology of organizational and pedagogical activities in the direction of "Biology".

This technology is expressed as follows:

follow the principle of environmental protection in the upbringing and education of students (nature as a habitat; nature in terms of ideas about the nosphere, bioenergetics; human nature, his health, activity as a species, etc.);

orientation to the restoration of spirituality in the direction of nature protection and environmental education;

analysis of the possibilities of each department of biology in the formation of interest in nature and space; education in the spirit of knowledge, compassion and love for the objects of nature and all living things in practical activities;

formation of a positive attitude towards nature, agricultural labor as an attractive, highly moral and economically profitable work (especially in market conditions);

to analyze the level of development of important professional qualities, competencies necessary for successful work in nature, among schoolchildren who prefer the biological direction.

The use of pedagogical technologies at the local and special methodological level in teaching biology paves the way for the organization and analysis of the educational activities of students, the knowledge of their shortcomings and their correction.

The implementation of a professional orientation in teaching biology increases the efficiency of preparing students for future professions, the conscious acquisition by students of knowledge, skills and abilities defined by DTS, the practical application of theoretical issues, their independent and makes it possible to master the skills of creative thinking.

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